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SKILLS

**Comprehensive, evidence-based
explanatory and foresight model
predicting the complex impacts of
ICT use on cognitive, physical,
psychological and social wellbeing of
children and adolescents**

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Comprehensive, evidence-based explanatory and foresight model predicting the complex impacts of ICT use on cognitive, physical, psychological and social wellbeing of children and adolescents

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Executive Summary

- Drawing on the empirical insights of the ySKILLS three-wave survey data, this report presents results from a series of simulation models that forecast the trends in wellbeing (as impacted by trends in digital skills) well beyond the observed data.
- In line with the ySKILLS model, the simulations differentiate between four different dimensions of wellbeing, cognitive, physiological, social, and psychological wellbeing. Furthermore, the report considers long-term trajectories of wellbeing differentiated between girls and boys, and between high and low socioeconomic status groups. Finally, it applies interventions to the simulation models that would improve the role of digital skills for wellbeing in a short-term and a continuous scenario.
- Such interventions are simulated to take place in a schooling context, aimed at improving digital skills and how they shape individual's wellbeing. Interventions are applied to all (simulated) students in an identical manner.
- First, we see that continuous intervention programmes are likely to contribute to higher levels of wellbeing, in particular for social and psychological wellbeing, and in some instances such continuous interventions contribute to closing gender or socioeconomic status gaps.
- Second, while continuous intervention programmes more strongly shape the developments of some aspects of wellbeing, even short-term interventions in some instances contribute to higher levels of wellbeing also in the longer term. For some scenarios, such as psychological wellbeing, short-term interventions contribute to closing gender gaps and improve overall wellbeing also in the longer term.
- Third, if intervention scenarios contribute to wellbeing in the long term, we tend to see stronger and more pronounced effects for interventions in earlier school years than later times, further emphasising the role of earlier, formative stages of one's school experience in developing critical skill levels and wellbeing.
- In sum, interventions, even applied to all youth equally and even only for shorter periods of time should be considered a useful instrument in contributing to (even only slightly) higher levels of wellbeing and (in some cases) somewhat diminishing inequalities based on gender or socioeconomic status.
- Yet, overall intervention programmes only marginally contribute to closing gaps in gender or socioeconomic status. Providing long-term interventions for targeted vulnerable groups may be a useful strategy to better close the more pronounced gaps in different wellbeing dimensions.
- This report provides a blueprint as to how data simulations can be used to complement and extend short term empirical observations. Based on our blueprint, it is now possible to refine the assumptions of the simulation model and the types of interventions. This report showcases the value of simulation studies in the field of digital skills and outcome variables.

1. Introduction

1.1 The ySKILLS project

The ySKILLS (Youth Skills) project is funded by the European Union (EU's) Horizon 2020 programme. It involves 16 partners from 13 countries to enhance and maximise the long-term positive impact of the information and communications technology (ICT) environment on multiple aspects of wellbeing for children and young people by stimulating resilience through the enhancement of digital skills. Starting from the view that children are **active agents in their own development**, ySKILLS examines how digital skills mediate the risks and opportunities related to ICT use by 12–17-year-olds in Europe (see <https://yskills.eu>).

The overarching aim of ySKILLS

To enhance and maximise the long-term positive impact of the ICT environment on multiple aspects of wellbeing for all children by stimulating resilience through the enhancement of digital skills.

ySKILLS will **identify the actors and factors** that undermine or can promote **children's wellbeing** in a digital age. The relations between ICT use and wellbeing will be critically and empirically examined over time.

ySKILLS' research objectives

To acquire extensive knowledge and better measurement of digital skills.

To develop and test an innovative, evidence-based explanatory and foresight model predicting the complex impacts of ICT use and digital skills on children's cognitive, physical, psychological and social wellbeing.

To explain how at-risk children (as regards their mental health, ethnic or cultural origin, socioeconomic status and gender) can benefit from online opportunities despite their risk factors (material, social, psychological).

To generate insightful evidence-based recommendations and strategies for key stakeholder groups in order to promote European children's digital skills and wellbeing.

1.2 This report

In an era characterised by unprecedented digital advancements, it seems a common assumption that young people's digital skills have become an increasingly important factor in shaping their general wellbeing. As digital technologies continue to permeate various aspects of daily life, and have become indispensable companions for younger generations, it is crucial to examine the potential consequences of digital skills on the trajectories of individuals. This report delves into the intricate relationship between young people's digital skills and their wellbeing, adopting a long-term perspective by employing simulations of potential scenarios based on empirical data.

Adolescence is a crucial time in which a range of digital skills are acquired and developed. Whereas children and youth nowadays almost inevitably make use of digital technologies for communication, learning or entertainment, they do so with varying skill levels to navigate these digital environments. Hence, whereas using digital technology will develop skills, this development can look very differently for different adolescents. Focusing on the relationship between usage and digital skills, Haddon et al. (2020) provide evidence for a correlation across a range of studies. Also the frequency of engaging with a diverse set of online activities seems related with greater digital skills (Mascheroni et al., 2020). Previous work in ySKILLS (Boomgaarden et al., 2023; Machakova et al., 2023) has aptly demonstrated that usage patterns show a very strong relationship differentiating those adolescents with strong engagement with digital technologies holding higher skill levels than those with less engagement. Based on this evidence, the present report continues to explore whether these skills actually matter for wellbeing. Hence, conceptually digital skills are considered the product of using digital technologies and are seen as one mechanism of linking ICT usage and wellbeing outcomes.

Based on the ySKILLS theoretical model (Smahel et al., 2023), our report distinguishes between four dimensions of wellbeing, all of which are crucial for the development of adolescents' future. While the primary objective of this report is to explore the potential impact of young people's digital skills on their wellbeing, we need to acknowledge that digital skills may affect different facets of wellbeing in very different ways. While digital technologies offer various opportunities for personal growth, connection, and knowledge acquisition, they potentially also bring forth challenges that may act detrimentally on other dimensions of wellbeing. Therefore, this report differentiates between social wellbeing, cognitive wellbeing, physical wellbeing and two types of psychological wellbeing. Based on data simulations as extrapolations of the ySKILLS three-wave survey data, it assesses the long-term trajectory of these dimensions of wellbeing, affected among others by digital skills. It does so by considering trajectories for different age cohorts of the original empirical data and by simulating these trajectories over a time span of ten years. Hence our results provide evidence for trajectories of wellbeing over a ten-year period for different age cohorts starting with ten-year old children and extending to 20-year old adults at the start of the simulation trajectories. Thus, while we focus on childhood and adolescence in our empirical data and the literature review below, our simulations extend well beyond adolescence into early adulthood.

Given assumptions about and empirical regularities regarding the relationship between digital skills and wellbeing, a particular focus of this report lies on assessing the potential impact of intervention scenarios for improving digital skills and their relationships with wellbeing. Public debate gives considerable focus to educational interventions to enhance youth digital skills, assuming such interventions may improve young peoples' life chances and overall wellbeing. Such interventions may take the shape of digital skills training in school contexts, for instance in terms of improving the technical skills to use digital technologies or in terms of media literacy programmes to learn about critical approaches to information online. Yet little evidence thus far has considered the effectiveness of such intervention scenarios. Our data simulations allow us to make an assessment whether and to what degree digital skill interventions may contribute to overall improved wellbeing in the long term.

Significantly, this report further places a particular emphasis on addressing inequalities and vulnerabilities associated with young people's digital skills and wellbeing. While the digital realm presents opportunities for empowerment and equal access to information, it also introduces new forms of sociodigital inequalities (Helsper et al., 2021). As a first step towards addressing such inequalities, the simulations consider differences in gender, knowing that both skills and wellbeing tend to exhibit gender differences. Secondly, youth's socioeconomic status is considered, differentiating wellbeing trajectories as shaped by digital skills between those belonging to higher and lower socioeconomic status groups.

Ultimately, this report seeks to shed light on the complex relationship between young people's digital skills and their wellbeing, taking a long-term perspective by employing empirically informed data simulations. Based on a baseline model, in this report we explore potential intervention scenarios that highlight the possible consequences of policies to improve digital skills in, for instance, educational settings. By furthermore focusing on inequalities and vulnerabilities, this report strives to inform policymakers, educators, and stakeholders about the potentials of digital skills training for wellbeing, ultimately aiming to promote a more inclusive and prosperous future for young people. Hence, we ask: What are the long-term trends in social, cognitive, physical, and psychological wellbeing as informed by digital skills? Are these trajectories in wellbeing univocal for everyone or are some groups more vulnerable and left behind? And can interventions which increase digital skills and their effectiveness for wellbeing improve overall trajectories and decrease inequalities in wellbeing?

For our report, simulation refers to the emulation of a real-world process over time. It involves creating a computer-based model that mimics observations about individuals within a given environment. This imitation allows researchers to observe and analyse the dynamics and outcomes beyond the actual information about the real-world processes. Such simulations here are based on simulated data, which are artificial, computer-generated datasets that mimic the characteristics of real-world data. These datasets are produced by the simulation to represent the observations about individuals in the modelled system. Simulated data are valuable for understanding how the system responds to various conditions and counterfactual scenarios (for example, interventions). Simulated trajectories then refer to the sequences of states that individuals follow over time within a simulated environment. Each individual in the model is assigned a set of rules or behaviours and the simulation calculates how these individuals evolve over time. Analysing simulated trajectories helps researchers examine the evolution of the system, identify patterns, and assess the impact of different interventions on the overall dynamics.

The presentation of simulation results in this report should be read as a blueprint for further exploration, also in collaboration with non-academic stakeholders. Simulating data from our empirical observations in the ySKILLS three-wave survey leaves a number of degrees of freedom as to the concrete modelling choices. For this report we have taken decisions that in our view represent realistic assumptions about the way in which the empirical observations should translate into long-term extrapolations. For the modelling of interventions, we are also transparent about the decisions, which may be somewhat overly optimistic regarding their actual impact. Lastly, it is possible to define groups differently in terms of considering different

types of inequalities. Hence, while we do have confidence in our results informing research and policy debate, the approach also should be seen as exemplary for creating evidence regarding long-term trends in a situation characterised by lack of empirical data.

2. Literature review

In what follows we briefly provide some rationale for our conceptualisations of digital skills and wellbeing, and review the sparse literature on the potential relationship between skills and wellbeing. These parts of the text are largely based on the ySKILLS systematic evidence review (Haddon et al. 2020) and are informed by empirical evidence (Boomgaarden et al., 2023; Machackova et al., 2023a).

2.1 Digital skills

In a world in which many facets of the lives of young people are percolated with digital technology and in which more and more daily life activities are relying upon having access to and mastering such technology, the role of digital skills is unlikely to diminish. By digital skills we here align with the definition used throughout the ySKILLS project and refer to the Telecommunication Union’s (ITU) definition of digital skills as people’s “ability to use ICTs in ways that help individuals to achieve beneficial, high-quality outcomes in everyday life for themselves and others” and to “reduce potential harm associated with more negative aspects of digital engagement” (2018, p. 23). To prepare young people for life in a digital world, caring for the development of digital skills has become more important. The phases of childhood and adolescence are now being affected by the use of technology more than ever before (Danby et al., 2018). Whether is the use or acquisition of smartphones and tablets in early childhood or the use of computers and whiteboards in educational contexts, young people are regularly confronted with technology. While evidence is accumulating regarding the individual and social factors that lead some youth to hold better digital skills than others (for short reviews see e.g. Haddon et al., 2020; Boomgaarden et al., 2023; Machackova et al., 2023a) it is important to note that the conceptualisation and consequently the operationalisation of digital skills do differ between studies and approaches and is not universally agreed upon (for an elaborate discussion, see Haddon et al., 2020, pp. 25-29). Our conceptualisation and measurement of digital skills then follows the ySKILLS projects’ approach, and focuses on the four main dimensions of digital skills in the youth Digital Skills Indicator (yDSI, Helsper et al., 2021): (1) technical and operational skills, (2) information navigation and processing skills, (3) communication and interaction skills, and (4) content creation and production skills.

Digital skills refer to the abilities individuals possess to effectively navigate and utilise technology in various settings. As technology continues to evolve and profoundly shape our personal and professional lives, understanding the concept of digital skills becomes crucial for individuals, organisations, and society at large. Each dimension of digital skills arguably plays a crucial role in equipping individuals with the necessary competencies to navigate and thrive in the digital era. Being proficient in these dimensions may be essential for individuals to effectively engage with technology, leverage its potential, and actively participate in the digital society. Yet, it also has been argued that individuals’ wellbeing more generally may be a product of digital skills.

2.2 Wellbeing

Wellbeing is a multidimensional concept that encompasses various aspects of an individual's life. The ySKILLS model differentiates between four dimensions of wellbeing and it is these dimensions that are at the focus of the present report.

One crucial dimension of wellbeing is *psychological wellbeing*, which refers to an individual's emotional and mental state. It includes factors such as self-esteem, happiness, life satisfaction, and resilience (Viejo et al., 20128). Psychological wellbeing is essential as it affects individuals' overall quality of life, their ability to cope with stress, and their overall mental health. Another integral dimension of wellbeing is *physical wellbeing*, which pertains to an individual's physical health and fitness. It encompasses aspects such as exercise, nutrition, sleep patterns, and body functioning. Physical wellbeing plays a vital role in maintaining an active and healthy lifestyle, preventing illness and diseases, and promoting longevity. In addition, *social wellbeing* refers to the quality of an individual's relationships and social interactions. It encompasses factors such as social support, sense of belonging, and interpersonal connections (Kemel et al., 2022). Social wellbeing is significant as it provides individuals with a network of support, promotes a sense of connectedness, and enhances their overall emotional and mental state. Research has shown that strong social bonds are associated with improved mental health, higher levels of life satisfaction, and greater resilience to stress, hence a clear relationship between social and psychological wellbeing. Lastly, *cognitive wellbeing* focuses on an individual's mental abilities and intellectual development. It includes aspects such as memory, attention, problem-solving skills, and creativity. Cognitive wellbeing is essential as it affects individuals' learning potential, their ability to make decisions, and their overall cognitive functioning. Promoting cognitive wellbeing is crucial across all age groups, as it enhances individuals' overall cognitive performance, academic achievements, and long-term brain health. Wellbeing thus encompasses various dimensions that are often interlinked and equally important for an individual's overall quality of life. Wellbeing incorporates how well adolescents do, both at personal and social levels and how well they handle change (Wassell & Dodge, 2015) and there is a great need to further understand children's and youth' wellbeing and their trajectories in a world increasingly dominated by digital technology.

2.3 Digital skills and wellbeing

In contemporary societies, digital skills have become central to successfully navigate personal, civic and professional life and to avoid growing digital inequalities (van Deursen & van Dijk, 2011). Several studies have explored the potential association between possessing digital skills and overall wellbeing, both in the general population and specifically among children and youth. Gaining digital skills can enhance individuals' access to information, communication, and various online platforms, which can contribute positively to their wellbeing. For instance, acquiring or holding digital skills has been shown to relate to peoples' sense of wellbeing (e.g., Livingstone, Mascheroni & Stoilova, 2021; Vissenberg, d'Haenens & Livingstone, 2022), but also to educational goal attainment (e.g., Pagani et al., 2016) or to a more favourable positioning on the labour market (e.g., Kiss, 2017). Adults with higher levels of digital skills report higher self-esteem, greater social connections, and increased opportunities for employment and education (e.g., Khampirat, 2021). Additionally, possessing digital skills was

associated with lower levels of social isolation, as individuals were more able to connect with others and engage in online communities. Overall, these findings suggest that digital skills play a role in promoting adult wellbeing by facilitating access to social, educational, and employment opportunities.

Research specifically focusing on the relationship between digital skills and wellbeing among children and youth also highlights the potential benefits of possessing such skills. The question about the impact of internet use on children's wellbeing has already been addressed in some prior studies (Dedkova et al., 2022), though the link between digital skills and wellbeing remains to a large extent untested, especially in a longitudinal design. Children and adolescents with higher levels of digital literacy demonstrated increased levels of self-efficacy, social connectivity, and digital creativity. These skills provided them with more opportunities for learning, socialising, and participating in various online activities. Furthermore, digital skills were found to positively influence psychological wellbeing among young individuals, as they were able to navigate and utilise the digital world more effectively. However, it is important to note that some studies have also raised concerns regarding the potential negative impact of excessive digital technology use on mental health and wellbeing among children and youth (George et al., 2018). Therefore, a need for further research to comprehensively understand the potential nuances in the relationship between digital skills and wellbeing in this specific population was identified. The relationship between digital technologies and wellbeing is complex, encompassing the possibility of both positive and negative effects on children's mental and physical health, life satisfaction or happiness. In spite of the substantial efforts over the past decades to establish whether digital technology hampers or fosters wellbeing, many questions remain (Dienlin & Johannes, 2020).

Relating to the evidence produced within the ySKILLS framework thus far, the overall picture regarding digital skills and wellbeing among youth speaks for a limited and rather complex relationship between the two. The systematic evidence review (Haddon et al., 2020) identified six studies only that would consider the relationship between digital skills and wellbeing. These provide incoherent evidence, given they examine rather different aspects of wellbeing. These different aspects and, in consequence, different measurements do not allow to draw overall conclusions. The report identifies some evidence that digital skills can have positive effects on wellbeing, for example on body image or experiences (McLean et al., 2017), while others demonstrated negative consequences on mental health (Duvenage et al., 2022). The report concludes that research evidence and that “the bigger picture of how skills might affect wellbeing is still to be established” (Haddon et al., 2020, p. 84).

The empirical insights from the ySKILLS project do add a more systematic approach to investigate the relationship between digital skills and wellbeing by incorporating the four dimensions of digital skills and four dimensions of wellbeing. Yet, the results are also rather mixed, at best, as elaborated in Machackova et al. (2023a): “There was almost no direct (causal, within individual) impact of any of the digital skills dimensions on any of the examined wellbeing dimensions. The only exception was a small increase in perceived academic performance affected by higher communication and interaction skills. Nevertheless, there were several associations between digital skills dimensions and the selected wellbeing indicators.

The psychological wellbeing, indicated by higher reported life satisfaction, was higher among children with higher communication and interaction skills and those who reported lower programming skills. Social wellbeing, indicated here by perceived support from friends, was higher among children with higher communication and interaction skills. Cognitive wellbeing, indicated by perceived performance at school (as contrasted to classmates), was higher among children with higher information navigation and processing skills and those who reported lower content creation and production skills” (p. 52).

The evidence reviewed above stems largely from short term, rather cross-sectional investigations. Only the ySKILLS survey data allow for a first glance at developments over a longer time period. This report provides a foresight model that attempts a much longer assessment of the developments of wellbeing. It appears that in analysing the long-term trend in wellbeing among individuals impacted by digital skills, it is essential to differentiate various dimensions such as social, psychological, physical, and cognitive aspects of wellbeing. With the increasing influence of digital technology in society, understanding the long-term effects on wellbeing as informed by digital skills has become crucial. By examining how these dimensions of wellbeing evolve over time for different age groups, researchers can gain insights into the potential consequences of digital skills on overall wellbeing in young adulthood. Hence the first goal of this report is to forecast, based on simulated data, the trajectories of wellbeing, taking into account empirically observed trends and differences in digital skills. It does so by looking at different age cohorts within our observed data.

Furthermore, it is important to investigate whether interventions aimed at improving digital skills can contribute to enhancing wellbeing. With debates in digital skills and media literacy policy revolving around how to improve digital skills in a way that would benefit young people’s lives, we here take opportunity of our forecasting models to assess whether digital skills interventions in a school context may positively affect wellbeing trajectories. Distinctions are made between long-term interventions, which involve sustained efforts over an extended period of time, and short-term interventions, which provide immediate, albeit temporary, enhancements. It should be emphasised here that modelling interventions in this report has taken a catch-all approach in that it is assumed that interventions would contribute equally to all students. In that sense we consider our approach as delivering first insights, while also offering a blueprint for more targeted interventions (see also discussion section).

Additionally, this report considers the role of vulnerabilities and how these could be addressed through interventions. Concretely it looks at potential gender and socioeconomic status (SES) gaps. Our empirical evidence thus far (Machackova et al., 2023a) points to the fact that there are gender gaps both for some digital skills (with female students doing less well on technical and operational and on information navigation and processing skills, and doing better than boys on communication and interaction skills) and for wellbeing (with female students showing less physical and psychological (life satisfaction) wellbeing). For SES we found that information navigation and processing skills are better among those with higher socioeconomic status and that these students also scored significantly better on all dimensions of wellbeing.

In a first step we thus analyse the trajectories of wellbeing in relation to gender and SES and consider in our simulated forecasting trajectories, we assess whether the existing gaps widen

or narrow over time, or whether new gaps appear in the projected trends. Furthermore, it is important to determine whether interventions are effective in closing these gaps and if they contribute to improved wellbeing across different demographic groups. By investigating the role of digital skills interventions in reducing gender and SES disparities in wellbeing, our results may provide information for practical strategies to address any existing inequalities. Understanding the relationship between digital skills interventions and the potential closure of these gaps is essential for designing inclusive programmes that promote equal access to improved wellbeing. Through the simulated data and forecasting models, this report aims to shed light on the effectiveness and impact of interventions in closing potential gender and SES divides in wellbeing over time.

2.4 Simulating wellbeing trajectories

Arguably we need to better understand long-term trajectories of wellbeing as shaped by digital skills and to consider possible gaps between different social groups and the ability of interventions to improve wellbeing and close gaps. Such evidence would potentially inform the planning and implementation of interventions in real-world settings and serve as information for policymakers and educators.

Addressing long-term trajectories, however, is much beyond the capabilities of existing and available data resources. Even the ySKILLS survey data, despite being unique in scope, do not allow investigations beyond a rather limited period of youth and do not extend into early adulthood. Therefore, significant investments would be required to collect relevant empirical data that could enable the testing of long-term trajectories for different social groups. Similarly, it would require some type of field experimentation to test for the effectiveness of interventions, with some samples of individuals being subjected to interventions while others would not. This poses challenges in terms of resources, but also raises ethical issues regarding the real-world implications of doing so.

The simulation setup presented in this report enables the examination of the gaps identified above. By generating synthetic data based on the empirical observations from the ySKILLS survey data we can address differential long-term trajectories. Utilising the individual trends and growth parameters observed in the survey data, we essentially extrapolate the potential continuation trends through simulations. These basic models then allow for the experimental implementation of interventions to enhance digital skills for improved wellbeing. It is emphasised that our modelling setup - while providing first evidence into the wellbeing trajectories and the effectiveness of interventions - can easily be used and applied to more complex modelling of interventions (see below).

Below we present the outcomes of 30 simulation models. These represent results for five wellbeing indicators (physical, psychological (self-efficacy and life-satisfaction), social and cognitive wellbeing), each presented for possible gender and socioeconomic status gaps. Thus, in each setup we compare the trajectories of wellbeing for female versus male students and for those students coming from high versus low socioeconomic backgrounds.

These models then are subjected to three scenarios, one without any intervention, one with a long-term, continuous intervention and one with a short-term intervention. In the first scenario, we simulate what wellbeing trajectories would look like purely based on and extrapolated from the empirical input from our survey data. In the second scenario we assume an intervention to take place continuously throughout our simulations. The intervention is improving digital skills in a way that they contribute to improved wellbeing. They take effect identically for each individual. The third scenario then applies a short-term invention only, which would suggest some special training in the school context to take place when students are at the age of 15. This intervention again is improving digital skills and they contribution to wellbeing, but its effect wears off after a while. Again, these are highly stylised scenarios, which could be further refined based on the blueprint setup presented in this report.

3. Methods

3.1 Simulation setup and model building

Developing the foresight model using simulation was carried out based on three closely interrelated steps. First, based on the three-wave longitudinal survey data (see Machackova et al., 2023a; Machackova et al., 2023b) for the detailed description of the dataset and underlying methodologies), a set of linear mixed effect models was specified and fitted for predicting five wellbeing measures (psychological, physical, social, and cognitive wellbeing). As each respondent provides up to three responses per year for each survey wave, we utilised linear mixed effect models to take into account the hierarchical nature of the longitudinal survey data. Each of five wellbeing measures was predicted as a function of the following set of key predictors in the model: (a) a lagged value of the respective wellbeing measure, (b) survey wave, (c) socioeconomic status and demographic factors (age, gender), (d) four separate summary measures tapping key digital skills (*technical and operational skills*, *information navigation and processing skills*, *communication and interaction skills*, and *content creation and production skills*, respectively), and (e) respondent-specific random intercept term. Four digital skills-related measures were then again predicted by a lagged value of respective digital skills measures, survey wave, socioeconomic status, and demographic factors, plus respondent-specific random intercept term, as can be seen below Equation (1) and (2):

$$E(Wb) = i + \text{lag}(Wb) + \text{wave} + \text{Age} + \text{SES} + \text{Gender} + \Sigma(\text{Skills}) + (1/ID) \quad (\text{E1})$$

$$E(\text{Skill}) = i + \text{wave} + \text{Age} + \text{SES} + \text{Gender} + (1/ID) \quad (\text{E2})$$

where i refers to grand-mean intercept, $\text{lag}()$ represents lagged value (i.e., value at previous year) of dependent variable, and $(1/ID)$ refers to respondent-specific random intercept term. (E1) therefore states that the individual-specific expected value of cognitive, physical, social, and psychological wellbeing at a given year (at year 2 and 3) is largely a function of its lagged value at the previous year (i.e., one's wellbeing at year 1 and year 2, respectively), current socioeconomic status (age, SES, and gender), and an individual's various skill levels at a given

year. Similarly, (E2) states that individual-specific expected values of skill-levels (i.e., technological, information, communication, content creation) at a given year are a function of one’s socioeconomic status and survey wave (i.e., time) itself, where survey wave/time serve as a proxy of hypothetical interventions (see section below). Here, our key interest is whether a set of digital skills are significant predictors of various kinds of wellbeing, and how such impacts dynamically unfold as time progresses beyond the initial three-wave of data collection. Given our focus on within-person dynamics and growth and the modelling setup as discussed here, we refrain from including a host of other control variables in our models.

As the three-wave survey data does not allow us to fully leverage the longitudinal nature of the inquiry nor provide specific guidance on the nature of the possible impacts of interventions on respondents, we alternatively set up highly stylised, abstract model specifications in which we can represent various different situations and setups regarding possible interventions on adolescents. That is, provided that key digital skills are influenced by the proposed intervention – the influence of which can be captured by looking at the specific wave in which such interventions are administered – these possible effects of interventions on wellbeing would be manifested by their indirect impact through skills, while treating the survey wave as the proxy instrumental variable for the interventions, as can be seen in below Figure 1a.

Figure 1a. General logic and structure of simulation setup

As a second step, based on the setup described in above Figure 1 and a series of fitted linear mixed models (following model specifications as in above Equation 1 and Equation 2) using initial three-wave longitudinal data, we extract the empirical covariance structure among variables and coefficients from the fitted models. This structure was then populated into three different scenarios (and respective simulation models) that represent different impacts of interventions on wellbeing through key digital skills.

- (1) for **the baseline model**, we do not assume any changes from our empirical mixed effect model setup as described above, yet only simulate data points beyond the initial three-wave data collection. As the purpose of this deliverable is to understand the long-term impact of digital skills and their influence on wellbeing, we choose to simulate such relationships for a ten-year time span.
- (2) for **the continuous intervention model**, we assume respondents are constantly and continuously under the influence of possible interventions targeting digital skills. While the exact nature of such possible interventions may vary, we simply assume such interventions (when administered) would generally produce higher digital skill levels on respondents over time (i.e., increased impact of time on skills), while any possible negative impact of skills on various wellbeing would be also diminished or even nullified. This would be translated as increased size of coefficients of time (survey wave) on skills, while setting the coefficients of skills on wellbeing to be zero if such coefficients are initially negative. While arbitrary, we set the size of coefficients of time predicting digital skills to be ten times higher than compared to those of the baseline model (i.e., interventions would produce 10-fold increase in digital skills levels than what would have been expected under no intervention scenarios), while any negative coefficients of digital skills predicting wellbeing are set to zero (i.e., there is no negative influence of digital skills in producing wellbeing). As we assume possible interventions targeting digital skills are constantly and continuously administered, these modifications on model coefficients are globally applied to everyone for a ten-year time span.
- (3) for **the short-term intervention model**, we assume similar dynamics as for the previous case, yet assume that possible interventions targeting digital skills administered as a one-shot, special types of interventions (e.g., adolescents receiving such interventions only at their age of 15), while the effect of such interventions gradually wear off over time after the intervention was first administered. We (again quite arbitrary) assume the effect of such interventions would be diminished by half per every year after the intervention, such that at age 15, interventions (i.e., time) produce 10-fold increase in digital skill levels, followed by 5-fold increase compared to the baseline level the year after, and 2.5-fold increase compared to the baseline level in the subsequent year, and revert to the baseline level starting from 3 years post-intervention and onward.

The last and the third step of the simulation process involved generating a set of synthetic data and actually simulating the impact of hypothetical interventions following the three different scenarios as described above. For generating skill levels for each survey wave (per year) for 10

years (see Equation 2 above), empirical correlation among exogenous covariates (i.e., age, SES, and gender) and their mean values were taken from three-wave longitudinal data, where a synthetic dataset ($N = 500$) following multivariate normal distribution were generated. We then generated wave-specific skills levels for each respondent, following Equation (2) above using this synthetic data, and then these skill levels were also supplied to Equation (1) above to generate projected wellbeing levels for each survey wave up to 10 years.¹ In this procedure, as described in the second step above, we generate three different possible intervention scenarios (baseline, linear intervention, and nonlinear intervention models), where we specify different levels of impact of survey wave on skill levels and on wellbeing. We repeat this process over 100 times per each simulation scenario, generating a total of 150,000 synthetic observations.

3.2 Measurement details

The simulations were based on empirical data measurements from a three-wave survey. The measurements of the dependent variables as well as covariates are provided below. The distribution of the variables in the empirical data is provided in Table 1.

Dependent Variables

Cognitive Wellbeing. Cognitive wellbeing was measured with the following question: “In the past year, how did you perform at school compared to your classmates?” With answers ranging from 1 (Much worse than them) to 5 (Much better than them).

Physical Wellbeing. Physical wellbeing was measured using the following question: “In the past year, would you say your health was...?” Answers ranged from 1 (Poor) to 5 (Excellent).

Social Wellbeing. This variable is a combination of several questionnaire items. Specifically, Friends support (3 items) and Family support (3 items). Questions included “My friends really try to help me” and “My family really tries to help me”, among others. All items ranged from 1 (not true) to 4 (very true).

Psychological Wellbeing (Efficacy): This variable is a combination of 4 questionnaire items measuring self-efficacy. Items included “It is easy for me to stick to my aims and achieve my goals” and “I can generally work out how to handle new situations”, and all ranged from 1 (not true) to 4 (very true).

Psychological Wellbeing (Life Satisfaction): This variable is a combination of 6 questionnaire items, for example, “[In the past year] I felt happy” and “[In the past year] I felt that life was meaningless”. All items ranged from 1 (never) to 4 (often). Items with negative wording were reversed to fit the direction of the scale (i.e., lower numbers indicated less life satisfaction).

¹ As this requires initial lagged value of wellbeing measures, we set this value to be identical to that of empirical value found in our three-wave longitudinal data.

Independent Variables

All skills variables were calculated from a set of individual questions. All individual items ranged from 1 (not at all true for me) to 5 (very true for me). The combined variables were normalised ($M = 0$; $SD = 1$) across all three waves.

Technological and Operational Skills were measured by a 7-item scale. Items included were: “I know how to adjust privacy settings” and “I know how to store photos, documents or other files in the cloud (e.g. Google Drive, iCloud)”, among others.

Information Skills were measured by a 6-item scale. Items included: “I know how to choose the best keywords for online searches” and “I know how to check if the information I find online is true”.

Communication Skills were measured with a 6-item questionnaire. Items included “Depending on the situation, I know which medium or tool to use to communicate with someone (e.g., make a call, send a WhatsApp message, send an email)” and “I know which images and information of me it is OK to share online”.

Content Creation Skills were measured using a 6-item questionnaire. Items included were: “I know how to create something that combines different digital media (e.g., photo, music, videos, GIFs)” and “I know how to distinguish sponsored and non-sponsored content online (e.g., in a video, in a social media post)”.

Covariates

The models included the following covariates: **Gender**, **Age**, and **Socioeconomic Status of parents**, which was measured with the following item: “Which of the following best describes your financial situation and that of the people with whom you live?” with answers ranging from 1 (We struggle to get by – We sometimes do not have enough money to afford basic needs, such as food and clothes) through 5 (We live very well – We can purchase luxury items, and still have money left over).

Table 1. Variable distribution over the three-wave survey, incl. all available data points

	Wave 1 (Mean; SD)	Wave 2 (Mean; SD)	Wave 3 (Mean; SD)
Wellbeing Variables			
Cognitive Wellbeing	3.33 (0.865)	3.28 (0.906)	3.29 (0.893)
Physical Wellbeing	3.50 (1.07)	3.23 (1.14)	3.13 (1.12)
Social Wellbeing	3.34 (0.582)	3.33 (0.599)	3.37 (0.580)
Psychological Wellbeing (Efficacy)	2.93 (0.662)	2.91 (0.677)	2.96 (0.672)
Psychological Wellbeing (Life Satisfaction)	3.00 (0.700)	2.90 (0.701)	2.92 (0.684)
Skills			
Technological Skills	-0.10 (0.98)	0.021 (1.00)	0.079 (1.01)
Information Skills	-0.028 (0.97)	0.012 (1.00)	0.015 (1.03)
Communication Skills	-0.02 (0.98)	0.01 (1.00)	0.02 (1.02)
Content-creation Skills	-0.02 (0.99)	0.01 (1.01)	0.01 (1.01)
Covariates			
Age	14.4 (1.29)	15.4 (1.26)	16.3 (1.23)
SES	0.01 (0.942)	0.03 (0.999)	-0.04 (1.05)
Gender (1 = Female)	49%	49%	51%

4. Results

Below, for each measure of wellbeing, we first present a summary of our analysis based on the three-wave longitudinal panel survey data and then we present the results of the simulations for each intervention scenario.

Before we present our results, we first introduce the way in which we visually summarise the results of the simulations. As can be seen in Figure 1b below, each Figure starts with a brief description of the actual scenario it presents, with the key dependent wellbeing variable and the intervention in the title, followed by a series of separate facets. Each facet represents a group of same-aged cohorts, where cohorts are defined as the age group in the same academic year at the time of the first survey wave, where they collectively progress into later school years and beyond. Within each facet, we present point estimates of projected level of wellbeing (as a coloured dot) with 95% confidence intervals as a vertical bar summarising uncertainties from repeated simulation of a single scenario ($N = 100$ repeated simulations per scenario per each facet). For ease of comparison within and across various conditions and wellbeing measures, we present (a) separate summary statistics grouped by two key socioeconomic factors (gender- and SES-based split) as a grouping variable with different colours, and (b) a red dotted global

reference line within each facet, representing mean wellbeing levels from the empirical three-wave panel data. As the goal of the simulations is to extrapolate possible patterns from our empirical data beyond the three-wave survey, we present extrapolated patterns for until the 10th year from the first survey wave with one-year intervals.

Figure 1b. Example plots summarising results

In the analysis of the three-wave survey below (and therefore in the simulation setup as well), we analyse our data collectively and present the results neglecting possible country-specific differences. We do so for several reasons. First, as a simulation model itself is already rather complex (therefore its results are quite information-dense) introducing another factor beyond key demographics (gender and SES-based split) adds much complexity, both analytically and visually, when communicating the results. While it is possible to find some country-specific differences in the real-world data in terms of the impact of various skills on wellbeing, we decided to discard these for the purpose of reducing model simplicity and keeping the results manageable. Second, and empirically as well, we do not find any noticeable impact of country factors when interacting them with various skills in predicting our wellbeing measures. It is possible that such country-specific differences exist, yet we do not think modelling them within this context adds much value for understanding the (already quite) complex dynamics.

4.1 Cognitive wellbeing

First, we turn our attention to our empirical model predicting cognitive wellbeing as a function of four key skill levels, lagged value of cognitive wellbeing, and survey wave. As can be seen below Table 2, we see a significant yet nuanced effect of survey wave predicting all skill levels (all $b > .029$, $ps < .001$), suggesting that as time progresses beyond the onset of the survey, respondents' various skill levels generally improve over time. Yet more importantly, above and beyond the impact of prior level of wellbeing level on predicting future wellbeing level ($b = .556$, $SE = .011$, $p < .001$), communication skills ($b = .025$, $SE = .012$, $p < .05$) and content production skills ($b = -.032$, $SE = .013$, $p < .05$) were found to be both significant predictors of cognitive wellbeing albeit their direction of influence was mixed. It is also noteworthy (yet as

quite expected) that those with higher SES ($b = .041$, $SE = .009$, $p < .001$) were found to have higher cognitive wellbeing. Females appear to score lower on their school-related cognitive abilities than male counterparts, yet this relationship was not significant ($b = -.001$, $SE = .019$, $p > .05$). It is important to note here that we did not find evidence of significant interactions among any of the skill levels and gender nor with SES levels, suggesting that the impact of possible interventions is not contingent upon one's gender or SES levels. This further (albeit indirectly) implies that any of the interventions conceptualised here are not likely to close the gaps between genders and/or between high vs. low SES-background adolescents (if any).

Table 2. Empirical models predicting cognitive wellbeing, three-wave longitudinal data

	Tech Skills	Information Skills	Comm Skills	Content Skills	Cognitive Wellbeing
(Intercept)	-0.839 ^{***} (0.095)	-0.010 (0.096)	-0.549 ^{***} (0.094)	-0.010 (0.098)	1.734 ^{***} (0.110)
Wave	0.100 ^{***} (0.007)	0.040 ^{***} (0.008)	0.032 ^{***} (0.008)	0.029 ^{***} (0.008)	0.011 (0.018)
Age at Wave 0	0.065 ^{***} (0.006)	0.012 (0.006)	0.035 ^{***} (0.006)	0.006 (0.007)	-0.018 [*] (0.007)
SES levels	0.048 ^{***} (0.008)	0.090 ^{***} (0.008)	0.060 ^{***} (0.008)	0.076 ^{***} (0.008)	0.041 ^{***} (0.009)
Gender (1=male)	-0.431 ^{***} (0.018)	-0.406 ^{***} (0.018)	0.044 [*] (0.018)	-0.193 ^{***} (0.018)	-0.001 (0.019)
Wellbeing at previous year					0.556 ^{***} (0.011)
Tech Skills					-0.003 (0.012)
Information Skills					0.012 (0.013)
Comm Skills					0.025 [*] (0.012)
Content Skills					-0.032 [*] (0.013)
AIC	43511.220	43940.126	45269.861	44355.597	14686.725
BIC	43565.277	43994.152	45323.902	44409.609	14768.287
Log Likelihood	-21748.610	-21963.063	-22627.931	-22170.799	-7331.363
<i>N</i> (Level 1)	16689	16614	16650	16581	6613
<i>N</i> (Level 2)	9615	9597	9591	9559	4860
Variance (Intercept)	0.476	0.485	0.381	0.502	0.000
Variance (Residual)	0.441	0.463	0.580	0.476	0.533

*** $p < .001$; ** $p < .01$; * $p < .05$

In the figures below and beyond, we present point estimates of projected level of wellbeing as a coloured dot with their 95% CIs in a vertical bar from 100 repeated simulations. In the figures, different coloured dots and their 95% CIs represent gender- or socioeconomic status-based split, such that we present separate summaries for boys vs. girls, or for low- vs. high-SES groups. Each facet represents a same-aged cohort that starts at some specific age onset of the wave (e.g., those who aged as 10 at the first wave of the survey are displayed at the first facet of the plot). As they collectively progress over time but show different paths and trajectories from those who were in a different school year, we present separate facets that represent different age cohorts.

Below Figures 2a and 2b present our baseline simulation model extrapolating the results of Table 2 beyond the initial three-wave time period (for gender-based split, see Figure 2a, and SES-based split, see Figure 2b). First, we find that without any intervention, extrapolated patterns of cognitive wellbeing generally do not go up beyond the level of which would be predicted at their age of 15, such that there appears to be some ceiling effects in level of cognitive abilities. We also see some negative, downward trajectories for those who are in the 16-year old age cohort and beyond, both for gender-based and SES-based patterns, such that their projected level of cognitive abilities generally goes down as time progresses. This is indeed an expected results based on empirical patterns found in Table 2, where we see a stronger (and more negative) impact of content creation and production skills ($b = -.032, SE = .013, p < .05$) than communication and interaction skills ($b = .041, SE = .009, p < .001$).

Figure 2a. Projected level of cognitive wellbeing, baseline simulation model with gender

Figure 2b. Projected level of cognitive wellbeing, baseline simulation model with SES

Next, Figures 3a and 3b describe the continuous intervention model simulation results—again with gender-based (3a) and SES-based split (3b)—by artificially modifying the impact of the wave on skill levels while setting the initially negative impact of content creation and production skills on cognitive abilities to be zero. We assume hypothetical interventions would create higher skill levels (e.g., a 10-fold increase in skill levels) while nullifying the negative impact of content creation and production skills on cognitive wellbeing.

A few things stand out when we examine the predicted patterns over a ten-year time span. First and foremost, while we do observe some SES-based discrepancies in these patterns (which would be expected by the positive and significant impact of the SES variable in Table 2), now virtually all respondents quite linearly (or almost linearly) change in their cognitive wellbeing over time beyond the initial 15-year ceiling point. Second and relatedly, the only exception to this pattern appears to be the 18-year or older-aged cohort (bottom three facets in Figure 3a and 3b), where they rather slightly decline over the years and revert back to initial levels later. This appears due to the fact that one’s initial age at the onset of the data is a rather consistent yet negative predictor of cognitive wellbeing (see the “Age at Wave 0” variable in Table 2: $b = -.018$, $SE = .007$, $p < .05$). This suggests that any interventions would be most effective in earlier school years than later times, further emphasising the role of earlier, formative stages of one’s school experience in developing critical skill levels and wellbeing.

Figure 3a. Projected level of cognitive wellbeing, continuous intervention model with gender

Figure 3b. Projected level of cognitive wellbeing, continuous intervention model with SES

While the patterns suggested in the continuous intervention model are quite effective in understanding the possible implications of a continuous intervention throughout one’s entire school years, such kinds of intervention scenarios are rather unlikely. In a sense, continuous, global interventions would be costly and challenging to implement logistically. More realistic scenarios, therefore, include one-shot, time-specific interventions the impact of which may last longer than only for a short duration of time. Yet, such a lasting impact—realistically speaking—would wear off over time, producing only marginal gains.

Below, Figures 4a and 4b depict such patterns of results (again, 4a presents gender-based patterns, and 4b presents SES-based patterns), where we assume individuals would receive a one-time, time-specific intervention when their age reaches 15. Since we assume every respondent may receive such intervention only at their age of 15, if respondents enter the survey after 15, they will be given no opportunities for such interventions. While in practice, such differential treatment would not likely gain support among various stakeholders, such a simulation setup allows us to naturally compare the impact of time-specific intervention and the importance of early interventions in producing the desired level of various digital skills among adolescents and its lasting impact throughout their formative years of experience.

Figure 4a. Projected level of cognitive wellbeing, short-term intervention model with gender

Figure 4b. Projected level of cognitive wellbeing, short-term intervention model with SES

Compared to the no-intervention (baseline) model, the short-term intervention model produces a sudden 'jump' in one's cognitive abilities, where such impact lasts two more years (with diminishing returns). While this is rather expected by the model setup itself, it nevertheless helps individuals achieve a higher—even if it is an only slightly higher—level of cognitive abilities throughout the entire 10-year time span compared to the no-intervention model, especially for those who indeed received such time-sensitive interventions early on (e.g., the difference in the average level of cognitive abilities over ten years: 0.013 for the 10-year-old cohort vs. 0.00002 for the 14-year-old cohort).

4.2 Physical wellbeing

Below, Table 3 presents the results of our linear mixed models using three-wave survey data, predicting physical wellbeing ('wellbeing past year') as a function of identical predictor variables as in Table 2. Again, we see very similar patterns of results where the wave (a proxy for school-level intervention in a given year) reliably predicts all skill developments, while physical wellbeing declines as a function of the initial age of the respondents (Age at Wave 0: $b = -0.033$, $SE = .009$, $p < .001$) and gender (being female: $b = -0.370$, $SE = .024$, $p < .001$), while those from higher SES backgrounds enjoy more physical wellbeing ($b = 0.066$, $SE = .011$, $p < .001$). In terms of the impact of various skills on wellbeing, similarly to cognitive wellbeing, only two skills are found to be significant predictors of physical wellbeing: communication and interaction skills positively predict physical wellbeing ($b = -0.058$, $SE = .015$, $p < .001$), while content creation and production skills negatively predict physical wellbeing ($b = -0.048$, $SE = .016$, $p < .001$). Identical to the results of cognitive wellbeing, we did not find reliable evidence to suggest the possible interactive effect among skill levels and gender/SES.

Table 3. Empirical models predicting physical wellbeing, three-wave longitudinal data

	Tech Skills	Information Skills	Comm Skills	Content Skills	Physical Wellbeing
(Intercept)	-0.839 ^{***} (0.095)	-0.010 (0.096)	-0.549 ^{***} (0.094)	-0.010 (0.098)	2.352 ^{***} (0.138)
wave	0.100 ^{***} (0.007)	0.040 ^{***} (0.008)	0.032 ^{***} (0.008)	0.029 ^{***} (0.008)	-0.037 (0.023)
Age at Wave 0	0.065 ^{***} (0.006)	0.012 (0.006)	0.035 ^{***} (0.006)	0.006 (0.007)	-0.033 ^{***} (0.009)
SES levels	0.048 ^{***} (0.008)	0.090 ^{***} (0.008)	0.060 ^{***} (0.008)	0.076 ^{***} (0.008)	0.066 ^{***} (0.011)
Gender (1=male)	-0.431 ^{***} (0.018)	-0.406 ^{***} (0.018)	0.044 [*] (0.018)	-0.193 ^{***} (0.018)	-0.370 ^{***} (0.024)
Wellbeing at previous year					0.472 ^{***} (0.011)
Tech Skills					-0.016 (0.015)
Information Skills					0.017 (0.016)
Comm Skills					0.058 ^{***} (0.015)
Content Skills					-0.048 ^{**} (0.016)
AIC	43511.220	43940.126	45269.861	44355.597	19364.008
BIC	43565.277	43994.152	45323.902	44409.609	19446.437
Log Likelihood	-21748.610	-21963.063	-22627.931	-22170.799	-9670.004
N (Level 1)	16689	16614	16650	16581	7109
N (Level 2)	9615	9597	9591	9559	5162
Variance (Intercept)	0.476	0.485	0.381	0.502	0.000
Variance (Residual)	0.441	0.463	0.580	0.476	0.882

*** $p < .001$; ** $p < .01$; * $p < .05$

Figures 5a and 5b show that physical wellbeing tends to diminish with age, as evidenced by the lower levels observed in older age cohorts, such as 18-year-olds compared to 10-year olds, for example. This decline is accompanied by a gender gap and a rather slight variation between high and low socioeconomic status groups within each age cohort.

Despite these differences across age cohorts, physical wellbeing remains relatively stable within a single cohort, particularly in later years. These patterns of simulated data show the importance of proactive interventions aimed at boosting one's physical wellbeing, especially in the later years of high-school.

Figure 5a. Projected level of physical wellbeing, baseline simulation model with gender

Figure 5b. Projected level of physical wellbeing, baseline simulation model with SES levels

Figures 6a and 6b show that continuous interventions are generally helpful in increasing physical wellbeing, based on the design of the simulation. Nevertheless, an interesting trend is observed in gender differences – initially, girls experience a decline in physical wellbeing (similar to no-intervention simulation results), but later rebound to their initial levels. In contrast, there is a visible constant improvement of physical wellbeing in boys over time. Interestingly, SES-based gaps and disparities remain relatively constant with linear interventions, and the effectiveness of the intervention is less pronounced in older aged cohorts.

Figure 6a. Projected level of physical wellbeing, continuous intervention model with gender

Figure 6b. Projected level of physical wellbeing, continuous intervention model with SES

Finally, Figures 7a and 7b show the effect of short-term interventions. There is a noticeable but small improvement in physical wellbeing when the initial intervention is introduced, followed by marginal increases over the subsequent two years. However, this initial improvement is regressing after the initial period, showing a gradual decline over time. The overall level of physical wellbeing in the short-term intervention cases is only slightly higher than the baseline for age cohorts of 10, 11, and 12-year-olds, which could signal the importance of early interventions in achieving sustained benefits. In the case of high and low socioeconomic status, the gaps stay rather constant despite the intervention.

Figure 7a. Projected level of physical wellbeing, continuous intervention model with gender

Figure 7b. Projected level of physical wellbeing, continuous intervention model with SES

4.3 Social wellbeing

Below, Table 4 presents results of our linear mixed models using three-wave longitudinal data predicting physical wellbeing (“wellbeing past year”) as a function of identical predictor variables as in previous cases. While our empirical three-wave longitudinal data shows that social wellbeing increases as a function of initial age of the respondents (Age at Wave 0: $b = 0.018$, $SE = .004$, $p < .001$) and higher SES ($b = 0.054$, $SE = .005$, $p < .001$), being female is associated with rather less social wellbeing ($b = -0.052$, $SE = .011$, $p < .001$). In terms of the impact of various skills on wellbeing, only communication and interaction skills positively predict social wellbeing ($b = 0.055$, $SE = .007$, $p < .001$) while content creation and production skills negatively predicts social wellbeing ($b = -0.016$, $SE = .007$, $p < .05$).

Table 4. Empirical models predicting social wellbeing, three-wave longitudinal data

	Tech Skills	Information Skills	Comm Skills	Content Skills	Social Wellbeing
(Intercept)	-0.839 *** (0.095)	-0.010 (0.096)	-0.549 *** (0.094)	-0.010 (0.098)	1.246 *** (0.067)
wave	0.100 *** (0.007)	0.040 *** (0.008)	0.032 *** (0.008)	0.029 *** (0.008)	0.019 (0.011)
Age at Wave 0	0.065 *** (0.006)	0.012 (0.006)	0.035 *** (0.006)	0.006 (0.007)	0.018 *** (0.004)
SES	0.048 *** (0.008)	0.090 *** (0.008)	0.060 *** (0.008)	0.076 *** (0.008)	0.054 *** (0.005)
Gender (1=male)	-0.431 *** (0.018)	-0.406 *** (0.018)	0.044 * (0.018)	-0.193 *** (0.018)	-0.052 *** (0.011)
Wellbeing at previous year					0.553 *** (0.010)
Tech Skills					-0.012 (0.007)
Information Skills					0.005 (0.007)
Comm Skills					0.055 *** (0.007)
Content Skills					-0.016 * (0.007)
AIC	43511.220	43940.126	45269.861	44355.597	9332.720
BIC	43565.277	43994.152	45323.902	44409.609	9415.598
Log Likelihood	-21748.610	-21963.063	-22627.931	-22170.799	-4654.360
<i>N</i> (Level 1)	16689	16614	16650	16581	7380
<i>N</i> (Level 2)	9615	9597	9591	9559	5333
Variance (Intercept)	0.476	0.485	0.381	0.502	0.000
Variance (Residual)	0.441	0.463	0.580	0.476	0.205

*** $p < .001$; ** $p < .01$; * $p < .05$

Figures 8a and 8b show that social wellbeing generally increases as a function of age. This is especially pronounced in the older-aged cohorts, such as 18-year-olds, in comparison to, for example, the 10-year-old cohort. This tendency is, once again, accompanied by gender and SES-based gaps. The differences in social wellbeing are more noticeable in the early years but tend to become more consistent and stable with age.

Figure 8a. Projected level of social wellbeing, baseline simulation model with gender

Figure 8b. Projected level of social wellbeing, baseline simulation model with SES

Figures 9a and 9b show a rather predictable increase over time given a continuous intervention. This effect seems to be primarily influenced by a disparity in model coefficients between communication skills and content creation skills (see Table 4). While the gender gap appears to be small, there is a pronounced SES-based gap in the patterns. Additionally, one's initial age seems to be a significant and robust predictor of one's social wellbeing, with older-aged cohort showing substantially higher levels of social wellbeing both cross-sectionally and longitudinally.

Figure 9a. Projected level of social wellbeing, continuous intervention model with gender

Figure 9b. Projected level of social wellbeing, continuous intervention model with SES

Through short-term interventions (Figures 10a and 10b), social wellbeing experiences noticeable jumps at the time of intervention, with the effects gradually diminishing over time. Nevertheless, the gains resulting from the intervention allows people to offset potential losses, especially among the younger age cohorts. While gender and SES-based gaps appear to remain substantial, the pattern induced by interventions nevertheless produce more positive outcomes for every respondent.

Given that one's initial age is a robust predictor of social wellbeing, younger age cohorts initially exhibit lower levels. Nevertheless, the early intervention for these younger cohorts leads to generally higher net social wellbeing levels both cross-sectionally and longitudinally compared to baseline scenarios without interventions.

Figure 10a. Projected level of social wellbeing, short-term intervention model with gender

Figure 10b. Projected level of social wellbeing, short-term intervention model with SES

4.4 Psychological wellbeing (Efficacy)

Below Table 5 presents results of our linear mixed models using three-wave longitudinal data predicting psychological wellbeing (defined as self-efficacy) as a function of identical predictor variables as in previous models. SES ($b = 0.051$, $SE = .006$, $p < .001$) and gender (being female: $b = -0.109$, $SE = .013$, $p < .001$) remain significant predictor of one's psychological wellbeing, while all of the skill levels (all b s $> .025$, all p s $< .01$) except content creation and production skills ($b = 0.015$, $SE = .009$, $p > .05$) positively predict one's self-efficacy. Identical to the results of cognitive wellbeing, we did not find reliable evidence to suggest the possible interactive effect among skill levels and gender/SES.

Table 5. Empirical models predicting psychological wellbeing (Efficacy), three-wave longitudinal data

	Tech Skills	Information Skills	Comm Skills	Content Skills	Psych Wellbeing
(Intercept)	-0.839 ^{***} (0.095)	-0.010 (0.096)	-0.549 ^{***} (0.094)	-0.010 (0.098)	1.569 ^{***} (0.078)
wave	0.100 ^{***} (0.007)	0.040 ^{***} (0.008)	0.032 ^{***} (0.008)	0.029 ^{***} (0.008)	0.031 [*] (0.013)
Age at Wave 0	0.065 ^{***} (0.006)	0.012 (0.006)	0.035 ^{***} (0.006)	0.006 (0.007)	-0.004 (0.005)
SES	0.048 ^{***} (0.008)	0.090 ^{***} (0.008)	0.060 ^{***} (0.008)	0.076 ^{***} (0.008)	0.051 ^{***} (0.006)
Gender (1=male)	-0.431 ^{***} (0.018)	-0.406 ^{***} (0.018)	0.044 [*] (0.018)	-0.193 ^{***} (0.018)	-0.109 ^{***} (0.013)
Wellbeing at previous year					0.495 ^{***} (0.010)
Tech Skills					0.025 ^{**} (0.008)
Information Skills					0.051 ^{***} (0.009)
Comm Skills					0.049 ^{***} (0.008)
Content Skills					0.015 (0.009)
AIC	43511.220	43940.126	45269.861	44355.597	10788.111
BIC	43565.277	43994.152	45323.902	44409.609	10870.279
Log Likelihood	- 21748.610	-21963.063	-22627.931	-22170.799	-5382.056
N (Level 1)	16689	16614	16650	16581	6956
N (Level 2)	9615	9597	9591	9559	5041
Variance (Intercept)	0.476	0.485	0.381	0.502	0.000
Variance (Residual)	0.441	0.463	0.580	0.476	0.272

Figures 11a and 11b indicate that psychological wellbeing (self-efficacy) generally tends to increase over time. The rate of increase is rather steep, especially compared to the other variables under investigation. While there are gender and SES-based gaps, the increase in psychological wellbeing is observed for all groups.

Figure 11a. Projected level of psychological wellbeing (efficacy), baseline simulation model with gender

Figure 11b. Projected level of psychological wellbeing (efficacy), baseline simulation model with SES

Given the continuous intervention scenario (Figures 12a and 12b), the slope is, predictably, even steeper compared to the scenario with no intervention. While the gender and SES-gaps are still relatively observable in the simulated outcomes, they are much less pronounced.

Figure 12a. Projected level of psychological wellbeing (efficacy), continuous intervention model with gender

Figure 12b. Projected level of psychological wellbeing (efficacy), continuous intervention model with SES

In the short-term intervention scenario (Figures 13a and 13b), there are evident "jumps" observed, particularly pronounced in the younger cohorts. These jumps signify substantial increases in psychological wellbeing following the intervention. The positive effects of the intervention, however, tend to diminish more quickly for the younger cohorts, whereas they persist for a longer duration in the older cohorts. These patterns remain highly consistent across gender and socioeconomic status factors.

Figure 13a. Projected level of psychological wellbeing (efficacy), short-term intervention model with gender

Figure 13b. Projected level of psychological wellbeing (efficacy), short-term intervention model with SES

4.5 Psychological wellbeing (Life Satisfaction)

Finally, Table 6 presents results of our linear mixed models using three-wave longitudinal data predicting psychological wellbeing (defined as life satisfaction) as a function of identical predictor variables as in previous models. Again, SES ($b = 0.051$, $SE = .006$, $p < .001$) and gender (being female: $b = -0.109$, $SE = .013$, $p < .001$) remain significant predictor of one's psychological wellbeing, while only content creation and production skills ($b = -0.022$, $SE = .008$, $p < .01$) and communication and interaction skills ($b = 0.028$, $SE = .008$, $p < .001$) significantly associated with one's life satisfaction, albeit with different direction of effect. Identical to the results of previous models, we did not find reliable evidence to suggest the possible interactive effect among digital skills levels and gender/SES.

Table 6. Empirical models predicting psychological wellbeing (life satisfaction), 3-wave data

	Tech Skills	Information Skills	Comm Skills	Content Skills	Psych Wellbeing
(Intercept)	-0.839 *** (0.095)	-0.010 (0.096)	-0.549 *** (0.094)	-0.010 (0.098)	1.231 *** (0.076)
wave	0.100 *** (0.007)	0.040 *** (0.008)	0.032 *** (0.008)	0.029 *** (0.008)	0.013 (0.012)
Age at Wave 0	0.065 *** (0.006)	0.012 (0.006)	0.035 *** (0.006)	0.006 (0.007)	-0.005 (0.005)
SES	0.048 *** (0.008)	0.090 *** (0.008)	0.060 *** (0.008)	0.076 *** (0.008)	0.056 *** (0.006)
Gender (1=male)	-0.431 *** (0.018)	-0.406 *** (0.018)	0.044 * (0.018)	-0.193 *** (0.018)	-0.144 *** (0.013)
Wellbeing at previous year					0.618 *** (0.009)
Tech Skills					-0.013 (0.008)
Information Skills					0.011 (0.008)
Comm Skills					0.028 *** (0.008)
Content Skills					-0.022 ** (0.008)
AIC	43511.220	43940.126	45269.861	44355.597	9881.552
BIC	43565.277	43994.152	45323.902	44409.609	9963.765
Log Likelihood	-21748.610	-21963.063	-22627.931	-22170.799	-4928.776
<i>N</i> (Level 1)	16689	16614	16650	16581	6982
<i>N</i> (Level 2)	9615	9597	9591	9559	5061
Variance (Intercept)	0.476	0.485	0.381	0.502	0.000
Variance (Residual)	0.441	0.463	0.580	0.476	0.238

In the absence of intervention (Figures 14a and 14b), the trajectory of psychological wellbeing (life satisfaction), reveals distinct gender and SES-based patterns. Notably, gender differences manifest as diverging patterns over time, with boys experiencing an increase in psychological wellbeing as they age, while girls tend to see a decline. Both trajectories level off and stabilise with age. This divergence is slightly less pronounced in older-aged cohorts. In contrast, SES-based differences also exhibit diverging patterns, albeit less prominently. In the high-SES group, psychological wellbeing appears to increase with age, while in the low SES group, it remains relatively stable over time, showing neither a significant increase nor decrease.

Figure 14a. Projected level of psychological wellbeing (life satisfaction), baseline simulation model with gender

Figure 14b. Projected level of psychological wellbeing (life satisfaction), baseline simulation model with SES

In the continuous intervention scenarios (Figures 15a and 15b), again, notable changes occur in gender and socioeconomic status (SES)-based patterns. The divergence in gender-based patterns diminishes, although differences remain apparent. Boys consistently experience an increase in psychological wellbeing, while girls initially show no change, with a slight increase occurring later. The rate of increase is steeper for boys. In SES-based differences, the diverging patterns mostly disappear. Both high and low SES groups exhibit mostly linear increases over time, but the lower SES group consistently reports lower levels of psychological wellbeing compared to the higher SES group.

Figure 15a. Projected level of psychological wellbeing (life satisfaction), continuous intervention model with gender

Figure 15b. Projected level of psychological wellbeing (life satisfaction), continuous intervention model with SES

In the context of short-term interventions for psychological wellbeing (Figures 16a and 16b) very slight, but distinct patterns emerge based on gender and SES. Gender-based patterns reveal a very subtle "jump" at the time of intervention, more noticeable for boys, with the effect diminishing in the subsequent years. Nevertheless, the intervention's impact persists, preventing wellbeing from reverting to pre-intervention levels. The intervention appears more influential for younger age cohorts, effectively counteracting a negative slope in girls and maintaining a constant level of psychological wellbeing. Boys consistently exhibit higher levels of psychological wellbeing than girls.

Similarly, SES-based differences closely mirror the gender-based patterns. There is a parallel very slight "jump" at the time of intervention, and the effect of the intervention is evident in maintaining higher psychological wellbeing levels, particularly for boys. Once again, the intervention seems more effective for lower aged cohorts.

Figure 16a. Projected level of psychological wellbeing (life satisfaction), short-term intervention model with gender

Figure 16b. Projected level of psychological wellbeing (life satisfaction), short-term intervention model with SES

5. Conclusions

The following presents a summary of the main findings of the simulation models above and ends with a short discussion about the possible use of the approach presented in this report. The results focus on the role of interventions for long-term trajectories of wellbeing and should inform policymakers about the usefulness of interventions in school contexts.

Cognitive wellbeing exhibits a generally stable trajectory with a slight decline observed after the age of 18. Notably, there is an emerging socioeconomic status (SES) gap in later years, where individuals with higher SES demonstrate higher cognitive wellbeing. Long-term interventions have the potential to absorb negative trends, yet they fall short of closing the SES gaps. Interestingly, short-term interventions only yield minor, but persistent positive improvements. Further, the results suggest that any interventions would be most effective in earlier school years than later times, further emphasising the role of earlier, formative stages of one's school experience in developing critical skill levels and wellbeing. Understanding the intricate dynamics of cognitive wellbeing and its dependence on digital skills thus remains essential for devising effective strategies to foster long-term cognitive health. It appears that long-term strategies are the most appropriate approach, but they should potentially focus more on low SES groups rather than high SES groups.

In terms of physical wellbeing, a clear gender gap persists over time, with boys consistently outperforming girls. While overall stability characterises boys' wellbeing, there is a negative trend for girls. Long-term interventions are effective in countering this negative trend for girls, but fall short of entirely closing the gender gap. Intriguingly, short-term interventions have

only minimal impact on physical wellbeing, highlighting the need for sustained efforts to address and mitigate gender disparities in this dimension. Overall, it again appears that early interventions are better in achieving sustained benefits in physical wellbeing.

Social wellbeing experiences an initially small decline but exhibits a clear upward trend in later years. SES gaps emerge to some extent, and continuous interventions play a pivotal role in enhancing the positive trend after the age of 16. However, these interventions do not contribute to closing the SES gap. Both long and short-term interventions lead to slightly higher levels of social wellbeing in later years, emphasising the potential for digital skills to positively impact the social dimensions of wellbeing.

Psychological wellbeing measured as self-efficacy demonstrates a strong upward trend over time, further amplified by interventions. Evidence suggests a gender gap in later years, with females displaying lower wellbeing than males. Yet, interventions did to some degree contribute to making gender and SES gaps less pronounced. This finding underscores the importance of targeted interventions to address gender-specific challenges in psychological wellbeing as a consequence of digital skills.

Conversely, psychological wellbeing measured through life satisfaction shows overall stability, with a slightly emerging gender and SES gap. Boys and individuals with high SES tend to report higher satisfaction. Continuous interventions contribute to an overall positive trend in psychological wellbeing but may inadvertently exacerbate gender gaps. Boys consistently experience an increase in psychological wellbeing, while girls initially show no change, with a slight increase occurring later. Short-term interventions have minimal impact on these trends. Yet, over time the intervention's impact persists, preventing wellbeing from reverting to pre-intervention levels. The intervention appears more influential for younger age cohorts, effectively counteracting the initially negative trend for girls and maintaining a constant level of psychological wellbeing.

It is noteworthy that long-term interventions aimed at improving digital skills and their potential impact on wellbeing are deemed to be overall more effective, albeit maybe potentially unrealistic in implementation. They have the most significant effects on psychological wellbeing, particularly efficacy, and social wellbeing. In contrast, short-term interventions designed to increase digital skills and their influence on wellbeing do affect wellbeing, but the effects tend to wear off quickly and only minimal gains remain over time. However, it should be acknowledged that these interventions hardly contribute to closing the gaps in gender or SES and in some cases rather increase such gaps. Our models assume strong overall receptivity to interventions and overall effects on wellbeing. The findings raise questions about the most appropriate time scenarios for interventions and whether interventions targeting specific skills and groups, such as females or low SES, would be the most effective approach to at least close gaps and avoid inequalities. It appears that interventions are more effective for younger cohorts and, to address inequalities, targeted interventions at, for example, female students or those from low socioeconomic backgrounds would be more appropriate.

It should be noted that the data on wellbeing were self-reported using different scales, which may introduce biases and limitations to the findings. Future research should strive to adopt standardised and more comprehensive measures of wellbeing to enhance the reliability and

comparability of results across studies. Furthermore, it is important to note that while we looked at direct relationships between digital skills and wellbeing, reality might be more complex. Likely, the link is mostly indirect, mediated through rather specific online activities or increased resilience to avoid harm from risky experiences (Livingstone et al., 2023).

This report and the results presented above should be read as providing a simulation blueprint and a framework that can be further refined and adjusted. The attempt was to present a long-term simulation based on synthetic data generated from the best available empirical evidence, the ySKILLS three-wave survey data. Yet of course setting up such simulations necessarily requires making assumptions, both on the likely growth trajectories beyond the empirical observations as well as the effectiveness of intervention scenarios. In particular, the latter can be used with much more nuance as presented here and thereby generate even more useful evidence for policy making. For instance, while we now assume interventions that encompass all digital skills dimensions, it is probable that the focus may favour some skills at the expense of others. Equally, one might consider scenarios in which skills interventions more strongly affect some (groups of) individuals than others, thereby potentially further widening or reducing inequalities. By doing so and refining the intervention scenarios, our foundational framework has the capacity to offer guidance for best practices in real-world settings.

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